

Facile electrosynthesis of nano flower like metal-organic framework and its nanocomposite with conjugated polymer as a novel and hybrid electrode material for highly capacitive pseudocapacitors

Maryam Naseri ^a, Lida Fotouhi ^{a,*}, Ali Ehsani ^{b,*}, [Saeed Dehghanpour](#) ^a

^a Department of Chemistry, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

^b Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Qom, Qom, Iran

Abstract

The [Cu(btec)0.5DMF] (H₄btec= 1,2,4,5-benzenetetracarboxylate acid) was electrosynthesized on the graphite working electrode by applying cathodic potential. The [Cu(btec)0.5DMF] grows on a graphite surface which results from the coordination of 1,2,4,5-benzenetetracarboxylate anions with Cu²⁺ cations. The electrosynthesized [Cu(btec)0.5DMF] was characterized by X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy. Furthermore, POAP/Cu(btec)0.5DMF nanocomposite film electrosynthesized on the surface of the carbon paste electrode by cyclic voltammetry. Different electrochemical methods including galvanostatic charge–discharge experiments, cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy are carried out in order to investigate the performance of the system. This work introduces new nanocomposite materials for electrochemical redox capacitors with advantages including ease synthesis, high active surface area and stability in an aqueous electrolyte.

Keywords: Electrochemical characterizations, Electrodes, Capacitors, MOF, Nanocomposite

Link: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0021979716306567>